

EFFECTS OF SOYBEAN PLANTING METHODS AND INTER-ROW CULTIVATION ON CHANGES IN NITRATE NITROGEN, MOBILE PHOSPHORUS AND EXCHANGEABLE POTASSIUM ELEMENTS IN THE SOIL

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10547569>

Abstract. As a repeated crop in the scientific work, in the conditions of the typical gray soils of the Okkorgon district of the Tashkent region, soybean varieties "Nafis" and "Selekta-201" were irrigated to a depth between the rows in the schemes of 60x8x2 and 70x8x2. As a result, in the 60x8x2 planting scheme, it was recommended to deeply cultivate soybean varieties "Nafis" and "Selekta-201" 16-18 cm, in the 70x8x2 planting scheme, 18-20 cm between the rows.

Introduction. As a source of nutrients for plants, the amount of nitrate nitrogen, mobile phosphorus and exchangeable potassium in the soil is important. Phosphorus plays a key role in energy metabolism in the plant organism. Potassium, in turn, participates in the process of synthesis of carbohydrates in the plant and performs its main function in the resistance of the plant to disease and drought.

A. Iminov, A. Qurbanov and Sh. Koziboev [25] data show that in scientific and research works, the treatment of soybean seeds grown as a repeated crop with nitratin before planting, the need for nitrogen fertilizers in plant care is reduced by 25-30%.

Z.M. Kushmetov [32] In the research carried out in Khorezm region, it was observed that there was no difference in the germination of seeds of five different varieties of soybeans in nitrogen-free and nitrogen-containing versions in moderately saline soils. However, it was known that under the influence of the nitratin strain, the activity of nodule bacteria was activated in the flowering phase and extended for 2-4 days and 6-7 days in the subsequent phases. He concluded that if soybean seeds and plants are fully supplied with nitrogenous substances during the growing season, their stems will be large, leaves will be large, and the growing season will be extended.

M.A. Tabassum [59] studies, when the seed of the plant was treated with nitrates, the root and plant length increased significantly. Plant roots and biomass increased by 20.0% when high nitrate was applied, but decreased by 21.4% when not applied, but there was no significant effect on plant dry matter

and nutrient concentration. It was determined that the dry matter mass of the plant increased from 616-625 g/m² to 694-697 g/m² due to irrigation.

Materials and Methods. The experiment consists of 14 options and is carried out in one layer in 3 repetitions. The row spacing is 70 cm, the row length is 40 m, the area of each option is $(0.7\text{m} \times 4) \times 40 = 2.80 \times 40 = 112\text{m}^2$, from which 56 m² is taken into account, the row spacing is 60 cm, the row length is 40 m, the area of each option is $(0.6\text{m} \times 4) \times 40 = 2.40 \times 40 = 96\text{m}^2$, of which 48m² is taken into account. It will be placed on a total area of 0.6 hectares.

Results. According to the conducted research data (Table 1 of 2020-2022), in the 60x8x2 planting scheme, when the Nafis variety of soybean is deeply cultivated at a row spacing of 16-18 cm, the amount of nitrate nitrogen in the soil layer 0-30 cm is 21.1 mg/kg, in the subsoil layer it is 21.1 mg/kg, phosphorus was 11.6 mg/kg, 8.4 mg/kg in the subsoil layer, exchangeable potassium was 258 mg/kg, 160 mg/kg in the subsoil layer.

In the planting scheme of 70x8x2, when the "Selecta-201" variety of soybean is deeply processed to the row spacing of 18-20 cm, the amount of nitrate nitrogen in the soil layer 0-30 cm is 20.9 mg/kg, in the subsoil layer is 14.3 mg/kg, and phosphorus is 11.0 mg/kg, 7.6 mg/kg in the subsoil layer, exchangeable potassium was 261 mg/kg, 165 mg/kg in the subsoil layer.

In the analysis of the changes in nutrient elements during depth processing of "Nafis" and "Selecta-201" varieties of soybean cultivated as a repeated crop, it was found that nitrate nitrogen, mobile phosphorus and exchangeable potassium differed in depth processing compared to the control option.

By the end of the season, the reduction of nutrient elements in the soil led to changes in these amounts in planting methods and deep cultivation of row spacing. That is, when the "Nafis" variety of soybean was cultivated to a depth of 16-18 cm in the planting scheme of 60x8x2, it was found that nitrate nitrogen decreased by 0.95%, soluble phosphorus decreased by 0.82%, and exchangeable potassium increased by 1%.

Similarly, it was found that nitrate nitrogen increased by 1.05%, soluble phosphorus increased by 1.1%, and exchangeable potassium decreased by 0.99% when the "Selekta-201" variety of soybean was planted to a depth of 18-20cm in the planting scheme of 70x8x2.

Table 1

Effects on changes in nitrate nitrogen, mobile phosphorus and exchangeable potassium elements in the soil of the experimental field (2020-2022)

№	Repeated Soybean Varieties	Planting scheme	Processing depth between rows, cm	Deep tillage depth between rows, cm	Soil layers, cm	Active forms, mg/kg			Active forms, mg/kg			Active forms, mg/kg		
						N-NO ₃	P ₂ O ₅	K ₂ O	N-NO ₃	P ₂ O ₅	K ₂ O	N-NO ₃	P ₂ O ₅	K ₂ O
1	Uzbek-6 (control)	60x8x2	12-14	-	0-30	22,2	14,0	256	32,7	27,4	255	14,2	26,4	200
					30-50	17,2	10,8	150	25,6	21,8	160	9,56	20,6	150
2	Uzbek -6 (control)	70x8x2	14-16	-	0-30	19,1	10,0	263	32,6	27,5	250	11,4	22,4	180
					30-50	20,5	6,8	155	25,5	21,7	155	9,3	18,7	150
3	Nafis	60x8x2	12-14	12-14	0-30	21,7	10,8	275	32,5	27,3	250	13,8	23,9	200
					30-50	16,0	6,8	160	25,6	21,5	160	8,6	21,5	150
16-18				0-30	21,1	11,6	258	32,4	27,1	255	13,2	22,7	200	
				30-50	21,2	8,4	160	25,3	21,3	160	9,7	20,3	160	
18-20				0-30	22,3	10,8	259	32,9	27,6	255	12,1	22,6	200	
				30-50	16,9	6,8	160	25,7	21,8	150	9,6	21,3	150	
12-14				0-30	16,2	10,8	260	32,8	27,3	250	14,2	25,6	200	
				30-50	13,1	7,6	156	25,6	21,6	155	9,7	21,7	150	
16-18				0-30	20,3	11,6	261	32,8	27,4	255	14,3	24,9	200	
				30-50	15,9	7,6	159	25,4	21,7	160	9,6	21,6	150	
18-20	0-30	22,1	10,0	233	32,9	27,3	255	13,4	23,6	200				
	30-50	14,9	6,2	160	25,7	21,5	160	9,6	21,4	150				
9	Nafis	70x8x2	14-16	14-16	0-30	20,7	9,2	265	32,6	27,1	250	15,6	27,6	215
					30-50	12,7	6,2	162	25,5	21,3	155	9,8	22,3	150
18-20				0-30	20,8	9,2	233	32,6	27,0	260	15,4	26,3	210	
				30-50	13,3	5,6	160	25,3	21,1	160	9,7	21,7	160	
20-22				0-30	18,6	9,2	267	32,7	27,4	255	14,9	25,6	210	
				30-50	13,5	5,2	160	25,4	21,6	160	9,7	21,7	150	
12	Selecta-201	70x8x2	14-16	14-16	0-30	19,1	16,0	259	32,6	27,1	255	13,6	23,1	190
					30-50	15,4	10,8	162	25,3	21,4	160	8,5	20,4	150
18-20				0-30	20,9	11,0	261	32,5	27,2	250	13,1	22,6	190	
				30-50	14,3	7,6	165	25,3	21,5	155	9,4	20,3	150	
20-22				0-30	18,4	9,2	267	32,6	27,1	250	15,4	26,3	210	
				30-50	13,2	5,2	160	25,5	21,3	155	9,7	21,7	160	

Conclusion. The conducted research revealed that according to the classification of typical gray soils in our region, nitrate nitrogen and mobile phosphorus are low and exchangeable potassium is very low.

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